

Ab initio modelling of the photoluminescence of
SrCl₂:Eu²⁺ - Direct comparison between density
functional and wavefunction theory-based
approaches

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ABSTRACT

Accurate *ab initio* quantum chemical approaches for the description of two-open-shell centers in periodic systems, such as the lanthanoid ions in inorganic host matrices, remain a challenging topic in computational chemistry. In contrast, experimental high-quality spectroscopic data on selected lanthanoid-based inorganic phosphors is widely available and offers a perfect ground to test new theoretical developments. One particular benchmark of computational methods in the field of $4f^{n-1}5d^1 \rightarrow 4f^n$ -based broad-band emitting lanthanoid ions such as Ce^{3+} ($n = 1$) or Eu^{2+} ($n = 7$) is the shrinkage of the metal-ligand equilibrium bond length in the lowest excited $4f^{n-1}5d^1$ state. In this work, we use the model system $\text{SrCl}_2:\text{Eu}^{2+}$, which crystallizes in a fluorite-type structure with cubically coordinated Sr sites, as a case study for bond length contraction along the excitation process—a behavior contrary to the usual bond-length increase (or breaking) encountered in most excited state cases. We performed a series of calculations, ranging from realistic periodic box systems to idealized molecular models. We explicitly compare wavefunction theory (WFT)- to density functional theoretical (DFT)-based approaches, offering guidelines on how to evaluate these methodologies for their suitability as independent predictive tools for the photoluminescence properties of lanthanoid-activated phosphors.

1. Introduction

Modeling and understanding electronic structure [1¹] are a rational approach for designing novel materials with desired properties, representing an elegant strategy in the pursuit of new technologies. Among the modern quests, the solid-state materials activated with lanthanoids play a pivotal role in the design of next-generation phosphors for optics [2,3^{2,3}] and spintronics applications [4,4]. Dependent on the lanthanoid ion and its environment, the emission spectra display sharp narrow lines, associated with intra-configurational $4f^n-4f^n$ ($n = 2 - 13$) transitions, or broad bands stemming from electric dipole-allowed $4f^{n-1}5d^1 \leftrightarrow 4f^n$ transitions. Both types of transitions play an enormous role in, among other applications, the photoluminescence of inorganic phosphors. Besides Ce^{3+} showing a broad $5d \rightarrow 4f$ transition, especially Eu^{2+} has been established as a standard activator for green- and red-emitting phosphors in oxido- and nitrido-silicates and -aluminates. In contrast to the strong experimental record, the theoretical approach to the two-open shell $4f^{n-1}5d$ states in lanthanoid-activated solid-state phosphors activity faces challenges based on the intrinsic complexity of electronic factors [5⁵]. In this work, we consider Eu^{2+} -activated $SrCl_2$ crystallizing in a fluorite-type structure [6,7^{6,-7}] with cubically coordinated Sr sites. This compound is an excellent test case for computational approaches based on a high local symmetry, retaining a high degree of a degeneracy among the 30030 microstates of the excited $4f^65d^1$ configuration of Eu^{2+} . In addition, the $4f^7$ ground level of the ion, $^8S_{7/2}$, is spherically symmetric and remains almost unaffected in a ligand field. Thus, the 5d orbitals are dominantly affected by the ligand field, resulting in a variability of energetic positions for the $4f^65d^1 \rightarrow 4f^7$ -based broad-band emission [7⁷]. $SrCl_2:Eu^{2+}$ shows violet $4f^65d^1 \rightarrow 4f^7$ -based luminescence at around 405 nm with pronounced vibronic fine structure and a correspondingly low Stokes shift at cryogenic temperatures. This is in line with the high coordination number of eight and also known

from other applied phosphors by now. The corresponding absorption spectrum shows two broad bands centered around 357 nm (28000 cm⁻¹) and 256 nm (39000 cm⁻¹), generated largely by the 4f⁷-[5d-*e_g*]¹ and 4f⁷-[5d-*t_{2g}*]¹ groups of spin-octet states.

Addressing these states in computational experiments is a true challenge, requiring a balanced treatment for the static and dynamic electron correlation, for the relativistic effects such as spin-orbit coupling, and even for the vibronic interactions along geometrical distortions. A detailed paper by Joos *et al.* [8⁸] has provided valuable insight into the complexity of dealing with excited states in Eu²⁺ and Eu³⁺-doped ionic fluorides (CaF₂, SrF₂ and BaF₂), and partly covalent sulfides (CaS, SrS and BaS), proposing efficient computational recipes based on multiconfiguration *ab initio* embedded-cluster approaches, that can provide experimental agreement in excitation energies within 5-10 nm of wavelength. Relatively recent studies further combine the embedding-cluster approach with time-dependent density function theory (TD-DFT) and excited-state dynamics, to reach excellent agreement with the experimental data for a wide range of Eu²⁺-activated blue and red phosphors [9⁹], for instance, SrLi[Be₄O₆]:Eu²⁺, Sr[Li₂Al₂₂O₂N₂]:Eu²⁺, Ba[Mg₃SiN₄]:Eu²⁺, Sr[Mg₃SiN₄]:Eu²⁺, Sr[LiAl₃N₄]:Eu²⁺ and Ca[LiAl₃N₄]:Eu²⁺. The paper by Joos *et al.* describes in detail characteristics of the severely dense spectrum of overlapping 4f⁷ and 4f⁶(5d, 6s)¹ spin-octet and spin-sextet states occurring above some 20000 cm⁻¹ for embedded Eu²⁺ systems. Complicating the picture, double-well potentials were reported for the higher-lying spectrum, originating from avoided crossings of genuine 4f⁶5d¹ states with delocalized energy levels. This kind of delocalized energy levels were classified as impurity-trapped excitons (ITE) and have been also unraveled for doped phosphors [10,11^{10,11}] based on Yb²⁺ and Pr³⁺, such as CaF₂:Pr³⁺ and SrCl₂:Yb²⁺.

A particularly interesting observation is that the equilibrium lanthanide-ligand distance shrinks [8,12,13^{8,12,13}] in the lowest $4f^65d^1$ excited states of many of the trivalent and divalent lanthanoid ions. This was first hypothesized by Blasse for Eu^{2+} and later demonstrated both experimentally and theoretically for a number of different lanthanoid ions. This behavior is unusual, because, in customary photo-physics, bonds typically elongate when electrons are promoted to virtual orbitals, with more antibonding character. We noticed bond shrinkage in our early work modeling $4f \rightarrow 5d$ transitions, with relevance in luminescence-based applications of lanthanide-doped solids [14¹⁴]. Researchers in experimental lanthanide spectroscopy are also aware of the anomalous bond-length contraction upon the $4f \rightarrow 5d$ excitation [15¹⁵], which is qualitatively represented in Scheme 1. It should be noted that the sign of the change of the equilibrium bond length in the excited state is irrelevant for the Stokes shift and the FWHM of the emission band, which are solely dependent on the squared or absolute value of this change only according to the Huang-Rhys-Pekar model. Thus, temperature-dependent luminescence spectra cannot readily give an answer to this problem.

Scheme 1: Normal (left panel) versus anomalous (right side) formal reaction coordinate along excitation process.

There are several experimental approaches that are suited to give insights into this problem. Among these, pressure-dependent luminescence spectra are easiest to record. From the sign of the pressure variation of the Stokes shift and FWHM at a given temperature, it is possible to derive a smaller or larger equilibrium bond length in the excited state. Alternative indications are a higher vibrational energy in observed vibronic fine structure, and excited-state excitation spectroscopy. EXAFS measurements in the excited state have always been of interest in that regard, but were so far unsuccessful.

The wave function theory (WFT) [16¹⁶] and density functional theory (DFT) [17¹⁷] are the two practical approaches in quantum chemistry for electronic structure explorations. However, their application to lanthanoid-based compounds is less extensive, due to the intrinsic complexities associated with the electronic structure of the lanthanoid ions. Multiconfiguration WFT in particular, which is yet tributary to various levels of approximations [18¹⁸], is conceptually well-suited for problems in magnetism and spectroscopy of transition metal, lanthanide and actinide ions, which are known to exhibit intricate electronic structures [19-21^{19, 20, 21}]. Using finite, embedded-cluster models mimicking extended crystals [22]²², Barandiarán and Seijo performed many successful and insightful WFT calculations dedicated to the spectroscopy and luminescence of the lanthanoid ions [10-12, 23, 24]^{12, 23, 24}

The phenomenological framework for tackling compounds with d or 4f metal ions (transition metals or lanthanoids), developed before the modern computational era, continue to be relevant as a bridge to interpret experimental data and is generically referred to as ligand field (LF) theory [25,26^{25,26}]. The WFT methods can be considered as the first-principles realization of the LF

paradigm. At the same time, the WFT-based retrieval of LF parameters in an experimental context is usually considered a measure of the computational accuracy.

DFT emerged as a pure theoretical approach that, in principle, circumvents the wave-function framework by solely relying on the electronic density as a key descriptor [27,28^{27,28}]. Its fundamental principles pose challenges for the direct application to lanthanoid systems, since DFT is primarily suited for non-degenerate ground states, whereas lanthanoid ions, except for those with an $4f^7$ ground configuration (Gd^{3+} or Eu^{2+}), have degenerate ground multiplets in case of the free ions, which become quasi-degenerate in compounds due to the generally weak impact of the LF on 4f spin-orbit levels. Another fundamental drawback of DFT is the access to excited states. Although this issue can be circumvented by means of the Runge-Gross theorem, time-dependent DFT [29, 30]^{29,30} is limited to one-electron excitations and cannot fully account for the spectroscopic problems of transition metals and lanthanide ions (see ref 1 p. 558, sect 6.4.4). However, it is possible to devise routes to interpret spectral data by DFT calculations given the possibility to derive LF parameters [31, 32]^{31,32}. Subsequently, these parameters can be implemented into LF phenomenological models to emulate the desired spectra. Some of us have tested the possibility of using such a DFT-based methodology to model the luminescence of lanthanoid-activated phosphors, [33-36]^{33,34,35,36} with a general perspective completed from our other works [37-40]^{37,38,39,40}. It should be noted, however, that multiconfiguration WFT route is still most adequate to theoretically assess the electronic structure of lanthanoid ions with non-*aufbau* configurations (see Reference 1 pages 588-600). Although spin-unrestricted DFT can provide converged solutions for lanthanoid-based compounds, the large energetic differences between spin-up and spin-down orbitals limit the interpretation of the electronic structure in the spirit of LF theory [41]⁴¹. Despite these challenges, DFT efforts on solid-state lanthanoid-based

materials deserve continued attention, as band-structure methods are tied to this computational framework [42].⁴² At the same time, combining DFT and WFT to investigate the electronic structure of lanthanide systems is a valuable approach, offering multi-faceted perspectives [43, 44]^{43,44}.

This article undertakes a direct comparison between WFT and DFT modeling of the $4f^7$ and $4f^65d^1$ electronic structures in a conveniently simple system, $\text{SrCl}_2:\text{Eu}^{2+}$. For that purpose, this work is structured into three parts. The first part probes DFT calculations with periodic boundary conditions to independently predict the optical properties of $\text{SrCl}_2:\text{Eu}^{2+}$. The subsequent two parts present computed spectroscopic properties of the $4f^7$ and $4f^65d^1$ active states based on embedded-cluster WFT calculations *versus* ground state DFT molecular calculations on idealized models: $[\text{EuCl}]^+$, EuCl_2 , free or embedded $[\text{EuCl}_8]^{6-}$ unit and the $[\text{EuSr}_{18}\text{Cl}_{38}]$ cluster. We discuss the phenomenon of shortening in the Eu–Cl equilibrium bond length in the $4f^65d^1$ excited configuration of $\text{SrCl}_2:\text{Eu}^{2+}$, versus the $4f^7$ ground configuration, which can serve as a benchmark for the accuracy of WFT- and DFT-based computational approaches. The bond-shrinkage at $4f \rightarrow 5d$ excitation in lanthanoid systems has been observed both experimentally and theoretically, but it has not yet received the in-depth attention it deserves. This work aims to provide a comprehensive overview of how these complex electronic states can be addressed by periodic DFT calculations *versus* embedded-cluster WFT setups.

2. Methods

The DFT calculations for the solid-state electronic structure were realized with the *Quantum Espresso* suite [45-47]^{45, 46, 47} using the Projected Augmented Wave (PAW) methodology [48,49]^{48, 49} and the PBE generalized gradient approximation. For Eu, we used the

Eu.paw.z_17.atompaw.wentzcovitch.v1.2.UPF pseudopotential based on previous works on the entire lanthanide series [50]⁵⁰ constructed with the PBE functional and containing 17 effective electrons in neutral state. The other pseudopotential files, Sr.pbe-spn-kjpaw_psl.1.0.0.UPF with 10 electrons and Cl.pbe-n-kjpaw_psl.1.0.0.UPF contributing with 7 valence electrons per atom were taken from the *Quantum Espresso* repository [51]⁵¹. Cutoff values of 150 and 600 Ry were applied for wavefunctions and charge density, respectively. Spin-orbit effects were not included in plane-wave calculations, aiming only to focus on scalar-relativistic DFT outcome. The unit cell was built starting from the crystallographic information file (CIF) of fluorite-type SrCl₂, available in the Materials Project database (<https://next-gen.materialsproject.org>) accessing the ID mp-23209 entry. The customization consisted in doubling the cell in all directions, inserting europium in the center and performing geometry optimization (for cell size and ionic positions).

Most of DFT calculations on molecular models were performed using the Amsterdam Density Functional (ADF) code [52, 53]^{52, 53}, with the built-in ZORA/TZP basis set. It should be noted that ADF uses Slater-type orbitals (STO) [54]⁵⁴. The ZORA bases were chosen for their rich content in primitives. However, relativistic effects were not included in calculations since inclusion of those effects led to wrong ordering of states in numeric experiments. Separate DFT calculations (including TD-DFT runs) were performed using the Gaussian09 code [55]⁵⁵, with Gaussian-Type Orbital (GTO) basis sets as specified in the WFT paragraph (*vide infra*). All molecular DFT calculations used the BLYP functional [56, 57]^{56, 57}.

Multi-configuration WFT calculations were done, both comparatively and complementarily using the GAMESS [58]⁵⁸ and ORCA suites [59]⁵⁹ with a SARC-ZORA basis for the lanthanide and def2-TZVP for the other atoms. In the frame of ORCA (version 5.0.4), the scalar relativistic zeroth-order regular approximation (ZORA) Hamiltonian [60]⁶⁰ was used also employing the

resolution of identity, RIJCOSX [61]⁶¹, along with large, automatically-generated auxiliary basis sets by the AutoAux algorithm [62]⁶².

The WFT calculations were performed in CASSCF (Complete Active Space Self Consistent Field) procedures, with seven electrons in twelve orbitals (related with the f+d atomic parents). The ORCA program was used for the efficient n -electrons valence state perturbation theory (NEVPT2) [63]⁶³ procedure, which was applied here to correct the CASSCF energies for dynamic electron correlation. Spin-orbit (SO) coupling was introduced subsequently to CASSCF or CASSCF/NEVPT2 steps. The non-degenerate $4f^7$ ground state corresponds to the 8S atomic ground term and the $4f^65d^1$ orbital promotion leads to 8H , 8D , 8G , 8F and 8P atomic terms, *i.e.* a total of 35 microstates (Slater determinants), given by the sum of orbital degeneracies. Although parity is usually neglected for atomic terms (as it is only a meaningful quantum number in cases of present inversion symmetry), it should be stressed that a $4f^7$ configuration has odd inversion symmetry (*ungerade*, marked with u subscripts), while the $4f^65d^1$ structure obeys even parity (*gerade*, marked with g subscripts). All the spin octet $4f^65d^1$ terms have spin sextet companions with the same orbital labels and even inversion symmetry. The $4f^7$ configuration has lower spin multiplicities, in principle down to doublets (with higher energy as the total spin decreases). The spin sextets appear in the 6P , 6I , 6D , 6F , 6G and 6H sequence. These considerations are drawn from general knowledge on atomic spectroscopy and from calculations performed on the free Eu^{2+} ion.

For the sake of interpretations in the spirit of ligand field phenomenology, as well as for a good convergence of the calculations, it is necessary to refine the active orbitals in state-averaged calculations. Practically, the ratio of mixing between $4f^7$ and $4f^65d^1$ configurations is an unrestricted parameter. A larger weight for the $4f^65d^1$ states reduces the overall gap with respect to the $4f^7$ -based levels, which may even lead to non-physical situations such as crossing below the

$4f^7$ configuration and is particularly prominent at compressed molecular geometries. Obeying the general convention, a $4f^7:4f^65d^1 = 1:1$ overall ratio was retained. In the framework of spherical or octahedral symmetry, each $4f^65d^1$ microstate had a weight of 1, while the sole $4f^7$ state had a relative participation equal to 35. In this way, the ensemble of 35 $4f^65d^1$ microstates is placed on equal footing with the $4f^7$ ground level. Although the recipe of averaging is somewhat arbitrary concerning different weight settings, we experienced that NEVPT2 reduces the dependence on this choice.

3. Results and Discussions

3.1. Plane-wave based DFT calculations of an inorganic phosphor: $\text{SrCl}_2:\text{Eu}^{2+}$

As a case study, we consider a Eu^{2+} ion embedded into a fluorite-type SrCl_2 host, a suited system for luminescence and computational studies [64]⁶⁴. The high O_h site symmetry of the Sr sites facilitates the insight into general issues of $4f^65d^1 \rightarrow 4f^7$ transitions.

The DFT solid-state electronic structure was modeled with the *Quantum Espresso* code [45-47]^{45,46,47} using a plane wave basis (PW) with ingredients specified in the technical section. Given the intention to confine ourselves to the DFT specific outcome, we did not employ otherwise commonly encountered techniques such as DFT+U [65-67]^{65,66,67}, which are usually considered to improve the performance of PW in compounds incorporating open-shell metal ions. From a certain perspective, one may judge the use of hybrid functionals [68]⁶⁸ and DFT+U as resorting to Hartree-Fock-alike levels of theory, i.e. amendments external to DFT itself.

The Eu^{2+} ion was placed in the center of a large cubic cell containing 31 strontium and 64 chlorine atoms, corresponding to about 3 mol% doping concentration at the replacement of alkaline-earth ions by the divalent lanthanide. In Figure 1, panel (a) shows the first environment

of the lanthanide ion as a regular cube, while panel (b) presents different views of the large SrCl₂ unit cell, with europium in the center.

The Eu(II) ion has an ⁸S orbital singlet 4f⁷ ground state configuration, allowing for a DFT calculation free of the caveats mentioned in the introduction. This enables a salient approach for determining the optimal geometry of the embedding, resulting in an equilibrium bond length of $R_{\text{Eu-Cl}} = 3.043 \text{ \AA}$, while the edge of the cubic cell is $a = 14.087 \text{ \AA}$. The Eu-Cl bond length is likely influenced by the surrounding host as a whole. At this cell size, a pristine SrCl₂ structure is characterized by an equilibrium bond length of $R_{\text{Sr-Cl}} = 3.050 \text{ \AA}$ bond length.

Figure 1. (a) the cubic coordination of the $\{\text{Eu(II)Cl}_8\}$ cluster and (b) different views of the unit cell, subject of the PW-DFT calculations. Note that, while the nominal cell composition is $\{\text{EuSr}_{31}\text{Cl}_{64}\}$, the visual representation in right side contains an excess of Sr sites (blue balls), having the $\{\text{EuSr}_{62}\text{Cl}_{64}\}$ count, resulted by representing atoms that otherwise belong to the neighboring cells, in order to complete the full cube appearance and the octahedral symmetry of the ensemble.

The *Quantum Espresso* [45-47^{45,46,47}] has a remarkable recent implementation, the so-called “two-chemical potentials” (TCP) approximation [69⁶⁹], enabling the emulation of an excited configuration (one hole in the valence band and one electron in the conduction band), which accounts for an average over the 4f⁶5d¹ spectral states. Following geometry optimization in this framework, we obtained a $R_{\text{Eu-Cl}}^* = 2.985 \text{ \AA}$ excited-state bond length and a cubic cell of $a^* = 14.070 \text{ \AA}$ (corresponding to $R_{\text{Sr-Cl}} = 3.046 \text{ \AA}$ symmetrized average). In fact, there is a slight

reduction of the bond length upon the orbital promotion and shrinkage of the entire cell. This is rather intriguing, as it is usually expected in photochemistry and the application of the Franck-Condon principle to find elongated bonds after excitation into antibonding states.

The tentative qualitative explanation would be that the electron promotion into the 5d orbitals enhances their propensity for bonding. In the ground state, the 4f shell of lanthanoid ions determines important optical and magnetic properties, but remains largely nonbonding, with a radial profile shrunk inside the ionic body. In turn, the 5d virtuals strongly mix with ligand orbitals, promoting partial covalent metal-ligand bonding [70]⁷⁰. The promotion of one electron into 5d orbitals offers the chance that, along with a radical character acquired by the ligands, in virtue of charge-transfer, the metal-ligand bonding shifts towards a spin-pairing, covalent-like, interaction between the ligand orbitals and the metal-localized 5d orbitals.

The density of states (DOS) for the {EuSr₃₁Cl₆₄} model of SrCl₂:Eu²⁺ in the ground state is depicted in Figure 2, together with the partial density of states (PDOS) for the f and d components. The spin polarization (seven unpaired electrons) is retrieved from the f-type α functions, forming a distinct profile between occupied and empty spin-up bands. At the Γ point, the degeneracies and spacing of f-type spin-up orbital energies are compatible with the range of ligand field expectation, obtaining 50.7 cm⁻¹ and 628 cm⁻¹ for the relative gaps of t_{2u} - and a_{2u} -type orbitals relative to the lowest t_{1u} -type orbitals.

There exists a negative f-type PDOS area, not visible in Figure 2, which is placed at higher energies. Having metal-based orbitals very different in α and β subsets is not favorable for interpretation in terms of ligand field models. However, this is an inherent trade-off associated with usage of an unrestricted framework, which is otherwise convenient. Attempts to restricted

open-shell calculations led to severe convergence problems. Concomitantly, we can assess both the advantages and drawbacks of DFT practice.

Figure 2. Density of states (DOS) from the regular PW-DFT calculation of the $\text{SrCl}_2:\text{Eu}^{2+}$ system, corresponding to the f^7 configuration of the Eu(II) embedded ion. The occupied orbitals are marked by filled curve areas. The partial density (PDOS) profiles of f and d-type orbital contributions are shown in blue and red lines, respectively.

The bulk of the bands can be regarded as effectively due to doubly occupied orbitals, with the spin-up versus spin-down DOS showing nearly identical profiles. The band populations, projected on the atomic shells of the Eu^{2+} ion, yield the following occupation pattern: $n_s^\alpha = 1.149$, $n_p^\alpha = 3.041$, $n_d^\alpha = 0.516$, and $n_f^\alpha = 7.035$ for spin-up, and $n_s^\beta = 1.137$, $n_p^\beta = 3.031$, $n_d^\beta = 0.468$, and $n_f^\beta = 0.129$ for spin-down. The sizeable population of the 5d-type orbitals, slightly polarized along the total magnetization, supports their role in the bonding. The 4f-orbital occupations are consistent with the $4f^7$ ground configuration of the Eu^{2+} ion.

The DOS and PDOS curves shown in Figure 3 describe the non-standard calculation performed in the TCP technique [69⁶⁹]. The shell populations of the Eu^{2+} ion, $n_s^\alpha = 1.168$, $n_p^\alpha = 3.048$, $n_d^\alpha = 1.172$, $n_f^\alpha = 6.413$ for spin-up, and $n_s^\beta = 1.148$, $n_p^\beta = 3.044$, $n_d^\beta = 0.536$, $n_f^\beta = 0.150$ for spin-down, which indicate a configuration approximately corresponding to $4f^65d^1$ for Eu(II) . The spin-up population of the d shell increased significantly at the expense of the 4f shell population, while the spin-down 5d and 4f counterparts remained comparable to the ground state results. The calculation of the excited state system, enforcing the limits of DFT, shows a significant change in the DOS profile compared to the ground state (see Figure 3 vs. Figure 2).

Figure 3. Density of states (DOS) from the “two chemical potentials” special TCP-PW-DFT calculation of the $\text{SrCl}_2:\text{Eu}^{2+}$ system, emulating the $4f^65d^1$ configuration of the embedded Eu^{2+} ion. The coloring and filling of the curves is similar to Figure 2.

The filled 4f-type spin-up components drop dramatically in energy (compared to the previous picture), merging with the bulk of the valence band. Along with this shift, the 4f-type spin-down virtual states entered the lower energy domain and can be seen by the large negative peak in the PDOS shown in the bottom panel of Figure 3. At the same time, the splitting of the occupied 4f orbitals in the cubic field is larger, as shown by the distinct peaks in the bottom part of Figure 3. The relative gaps in the t_{1u} -, t_{2u} - and, a_{2u} -type spin-up sequences are 1264.5 cm^{-1} and 3226.6 cm^{-1} , respectively, sensibly larger than expected for a ligand field range. Such changes in the 4f orbitals are counter-intuitive, being an undesired consequence of the TCP technique, which otherwise describes well, in global manner, the phenomenon of the $4f \rightarrow 5d$ orbital promotion. As can be seen in Figure 3, a d-type component forms an occupied satellite just below the conduction band. The difference between the total energies of the systems corresponding to excited (f^6d) and ground (f^7) embedded Eu^{2+} , about 23400 cm^{-1} , is compatible with the observed luminescence, forming a band with vibronic progression in the $24000 - 25000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ range [77Error! Bookmark not defined.].

As a partial conclusion, the PW-DFT calculations with the new TCP method [69⁶⁹] can in principle reproduce the steady-state photophysics of such challenging two-open shell lanthanoid systems in the solid state although certain calculation details such as drastically different spin-up and spin-down orbital sets are not in line with the underlying ligand field paradigms.

3.2 Idealized systems: linear ClEuCl molecule in DFT and WFT.

In the following, we scrutinize the phenomenon of bond length reduction upon a $4f^7 \rightarrow 4f^65d^1$ excitation using a simplified starting point, the linear $[\text{EuCl}_2]$ molecule. The standard route to excited states in DFT framework would be the time-dependent (TD) method [29,30^{29,30}]. However, TD-DFT approaches to the spectroscopy of lanthanide complexes does not produce electronic states compatible with ligand field ideas (see ref 1 p. 558). Specifically, in our study, the analysis

of the TD natural transition orbitals did not reveal functions with dominant d-type character, at least not within the reasonable range of the lowest 20-30 states.

To address this technical difficulty, the ADF (Amsterdam Density Functional) suite [52⁵²] provides a useful approach by allowing non-*aufbau* configurations and fractional occupations through symmetry representations. In conceptual DFT, fractional occupations are allowed [71,72]^{71,72}, but only a few existing codes enable such a feature. A non-*aufbau* configuration, i.e. having inverted populations with lower occupation of energetically lower orbitals and imposed promotion of electrons into virtuals can emulate an excited state. This may break the DFT limitation to ground states but semi-quantitatively, it can be taken as a rough measure of an excited configuration. We have used this ADF feature to model the desired $4f^6 5d^1$ configurations.

The fractional occupations allow us to address situations with degenerate ground states, creating artificial non-degenerate electronic states by averaging of the orbital populations. For instance, a $4f^6$ configuration leads to a seven-fold orbitally degenerate 7F term, which poses problems to DFT. The resulting different orbital shapes will lead to varying density maps of the configurations in the set, for which currently employed exchange-correlation functionals artificially result in different energies for the configurations expected to be degenerate. By enforcing a $6/7$ fractional occupation of the atomic $4f$ orbitals in the $4f^6$ configuration, the orbital degree of freedom of the atomic functions is removed, which leads to an artificial density map drawn solely by the radial part of the atomic function. Similarly, a $5d^1$ configuration can be treated smearing the one electron among the five orbitals each one with an effective averaged $1/5$ population. Thus, an orbitally degenerate $4f^6 5d^1$ configuration can be imposed in DFT with an effective $f^{7 \times (6/7)\alpha} d^{5 \times (1/5)\alpha}$ fractional occupation scheme. The linear $[\text{EuCl}_2]$ system obeys a centrosymmetric $D_{\infty h}$ point group with f and d orbitals spanning different representations, i.e. $f \rightarrow \sigma_u + 2\pi_u + 2\delta_u + 2\phi_u$, and $d \rightarrow \sigma_g + 2\pi_g$

+ $2\delta_g$. If the degeneracy is annihilated by population averaging, then the $4f^7$ configuration of the linear EuCl_2 molecule formally transforms like a Σ_u representation (because of the odd electron count in the *ungerade* inversion symmetry), while the $4f^65d^1$ configuration transforms like a Σ_g representation (having an even number of electrons in *ungerade* orbitals and one in the *gerade* d-type shell). While for the $4f^7$ configuration, the Σ_u label designates the real representation of the non-degenerate ground state, the Σ_g representation of the excited $4f^65d^1$ configuration is artificially generated by the orbital averaging approach. This may be interpreted as one of the lowest energetic states of the $4f^65d^1$ excited configuration with that irreducible representation different from that of the real ground state. Since the symmetry-distinct electronic structure objects are not mutually interacting, Gunnarsson and Lundqvist were able to demonstrate that the Hohenberg-Kohn theorem can be in principle also extended to those excited states with a different irreducible representation of that of the ground state in a given point group. Using this approach allows to perform a DFT-based optimization of the Eu–Cl equilibrium bond length in both the lower energetic $4f^7$ and excited $4f^65d^1$ configuration (see Table 1).

In a restricted open shell treatment confined to spin octet configuration, the ground state adopts an energy ordering of the singly occupied f-type orbitals given by the $\varphi_u < \delta_u < \pi_u < \sigma_u$ sequence expected from Angular Overlap Model (AOM) [73-76]^{73,74,75,76} of the ligand field theory.

Table 1. Computed Eu-Cl bond length for the [ClEuCl] symmetric linear molecule, in ground and excited configurations. For the last line, the values in parentheses correspond to results after NEVPT2 corrections to CASSCF(7,12) calculations.

Method	R_{min} (f^7 config), in Å	R_{min} (f^6d config), in Å
ADF, Restricted, with symmetry and population control	2.653	2.640
ADF, Unrestricted, with symmetry and population control	2.665	2.618
ADF Restricted, without symmetry, with population control	2.653	2.638
ADF Unrestricted, without symmetry, with population control	2.665	2.620
DFT/GTO, Unrestricted, with symmetry, no population control. TD taken as excited f^6d configuration.	2.667	3.220
CASSCF/GTO/ground state as f^7 case, first excited state as representative for f^6d	2.748 (2.718)	2.653 (2.495)

It is evident that except for the TD-DFT entry, the Eu-Cl bond length is generally shortened in the excited $4f^65d^1$ configuration compared to that in the $4f^7$ ground configuration in both DFT- and WFT-based treatments. We already indicated above that TD-DFT does not capture a set of excited states readily assignable to the $4f^65d^1$ configuration. This issue is related to the fact that the TD required to obtain information about excited levels in a limited way is yet based on orbitals produced in the ground state. In the $4f^7$ -based ground state, there is no reliable information about the empty 5d-type functions, because the virtuals themselves are not objects of the energy minimization, resulting only as the orthogonal complement of the optimized occupied orbitals. Therefore, one may not expect a good account by TD-DFT of the concerned $4f^7 \rightarrow 4f^65d^1$

transition. This means that DFT itself has intrinsic difficulties in accounting the spectroscopic subtleties of lanthanoid-based compounds.

The optimized geometries computed with or without symmetry are similar, I.e, in these cases the resulting configuration is *aufbau*-type with singly-occupied orbitals on top of the doubly occupied ones. The success of the (time-independent!) DFT formally represented by the qualitative match with the WFT result (see Table 1) is generated by the rather radical approximation of fractional occupation of the Kohn-Sham orbitals enabled by the ADF code. An interesting point to the DFT vs. WFT debate is raised by optimized bond lengths for a charged $[\text{EuCl}]^+$ diatomic molecule using the same series of techniques. In this case, WFT leads to a longer bond in the ground state than in the first $4f^65d^1$ excited state, i.e. 2.613 Å vs. 2.565 Å. This situation is analogous to the $[\text{EuCl}_2]$ case. In contrast, all DFT attempts result in a longer bond in the excited state. The counterpart values corresponding to the first four entries in Table 1 are, for the $[\text{EuCl}]^+$ case, 2.484, 2.581 / 2.489, 2.636 / 2.484, 2.557 / 2.489, 2.502 Å.

We have attempted various DFT calculations for $[\text{EuCl}]^+$ with population control. However, these calculations failed because the asymmetric diatomic molecule lacks an inversion center given a $C_{\infty v}$ point symmetry. Consequently, both $4f^7$ and $4f^65d^1$ configurations share the same irreducible representation $^8\Sigma$ of the resulting multielectron state upon fractional orbital occupation. Classic DFT runs into a problematic situation here given that it requires one unambiguous reference ground state. This is the cause of the erroneous result regarding the bond length of $[\text{EuCl}]^+$ in the $4f^65d^1$ excited state. Geometry optimization of $[\text{EuCl}]^+$ by TD-DFT led to a similar, erroneous elongation of the bond length in the excited $4f^65d^1$ configuration, trend which is opposite to that unveiled by the WFT calculations, and in analogy to the neutral EuCl_2 molecule.

In the following, we will analyze the bonding factors using another ADF specific feature: the possibility to remove virtual orbitals from constituting fragments. The left panel of Figure 4 shows a progressive series of orbital deletions for both $4f^7$ and $4f^65d^1$ configurations as a function of the Eu–Cl bond length. The full calculations, without orbital deletions, are shown as tick continuous lines, blue for $4f^7$ and red for $4f^65d^1$ cases, keeping the colors for the given series and marking the various orbital deletion settings by different symbols. A given deletion scheme keeps the same symbol in the lower and upper branches.

Figure 4. (a) Results from ADF numeric experiments on EuCl_2 , performing different schemes of virtual orbitals deletion from Eu^{2+} and Cl^- fragments. The $4f^7$ configuration in red, the $4f^65d^1$ in blue. Continuous line- complete fragments. Symbols for deleted shells: +/s-Eu, x/p-Eu, Δ/d-Eu, o/f-Eu, ∇/spdf-Eu, □/spd-Cl, ◇ spdf-Eu & spd-Cl. (b) Potential energy curves for the EuCl_2 linear molecule calculated by CASSCF(7,12) followed by NEVPT2 corrections. The lowered blue curve is the interpolation of computed geometries (marked with circles), corresponding to the $4f^7$ ground state. The red lines are excited spin-octet multiplets emerging from the $4f^65d^1$ configuration.

The removal of p or f empty orbitals from Eu(II) (marked by \times and o symbols, respectively) leads to negligible changes in the formation energy, these points being almost coincidental with the continuous lines. The removal of s virtuals (+ symbols) from Eu(II) shows almost no effect in the $4f^7$ case (the curve being overlapped with the p and f deletions) and determines a small overall energy rise in the $4f^65d^1$ case. The elimination of d empty shells (marked by Δ symbols) causes a sensible loss of bonding (i.e. energy rising), these curves, in both the $4f^7$ and $4f^65d^1$ cases, being close to those having all virtuals (s, p, d and f) eliminated (case marked by ∇). Then, one may conclude that the most important bonding contribution is ensured by the Eu(II) d-type empty orbitals acting as acceptors for the density donated by ligands. This is also meaningful from a molecular orbital approach: The 5d orbitals and the ligand orbitals are similar in energy and symmetry-adapted, which enables chemical bonding between Eu(II) and the surrounding ligands.

At the same time, one notes a sensible shift at the deletion of all the virtuals from chloride anions (see points marked by \square). This cannot properly be interpreted as metal-to-ligand back donation. In turn, it is due to aspherical deformation of the rather polarizable anions, an effect implying the mixing of occupied and unoccupied functions of the chlorine atoms. Then, the removal of empty shells impedes the local polarization. The sum of bonding losses when all the virtuals are deleted, on either metal or ligand, is almost equal to the destabilization after complete removal of virtuals on both fragments.

In the relatively large distance domain represented in left side of Figure 4, the shift between the minima corresponding to the full calculations on $4f^7$ and $4f^65d^1$ configurations is barely visible, but it occurs in the full calculations and in other situations as well. The elimination of ligand-based orbitals keeps the minimum around those of the full curve, suggesting that the main bonding is not essentially disturbed. At the same time is clearly seen that curves implying the drop of 5d-type

orbitals reach their minima at larger bond lengths (in both $4f^7$ and $4f^65d^1$ series). The removal-driven bond elongation is larger in the $4f^7$ -based than in the $4f^65d^1$ -based states leading to an equilibrium bond length shrinkage in the excited state. A subtle noteworthy detail is that in the $4f^65d^1$ case, the removal of d shell components does not have the same effect as it does in an $4f^7$ -type calculation. Specifically, in the $4f^7$ ground state it is possible to erase all the five d orbitals, whereas only four of them are available to deletion in the emulated $4f^65d^1$ excited state, since one 5d-orbital is now occupied (with occupation smeared on all molecular orbitals originating from 5d).

In the ADF output, the total bonding energy can be separated into the following components: an electrostatic part (due to classical Coulomb interactions between fragments), Pauli repulsion (due to anti-symmetrized wave functions, incorporating exchange companions of the Coulomb integrals), and orbital interactions (due to inter-center overlap and transfer effects) [81].⁷⁷ The variation of summed electrostatic and Pauli terms is the same for all the curves shown in Figure 4a, the mutual differences in the total energy being due to the orbital part. At the same time, this sum is very close to the curve corresponding to the $4f^7$ case having all the Eu^{2+} -based and Cl^- -based virtuals removed. At a given geometry, all the calculations show the same values for respective Coulomb and Pauli terms.

The right panel of Figure 4 shows the spin octet states from multiconfiguration calculations on linear EuCl_2 , namely CASSCF amended with a second order perturbation theory (NEVPT2) treatment. The energy window contains 35 excited levels (some grouped in double degenerate pairs) corresponding to high-spin $4f^7 \rightarrow 4f^65d^1$ single excitations. Most of the excited states show minima at shorter bond lengths compared to the ground state. The first excited state exhibits the most pronounced shrinkage in the equilibrium metal-ligand bond length (see values in the last row

of Table 1). By visual inspection, the series of excited states can be grouped into bundles that can be attributed to successively higher excitations into δ , π and σ components of the d orbitals. The splitting within each bundle is due to inter-electronic effects and the small ligand field splitting of the 4f shell. Qualitatively, the following ranking can be established: $r_{\text{EuCl}}(4f^6 5d_\delta) < r_{\text{EuCl}}(4f^6 5d_\pi) < r_{\text{EuCl}}(4f^6 5d_\sigma)$. For the higher-energy states, their minima tend to match the energetic minimum of the ground state.

Corroborating observations from DFT and CASSCF, one may conceive a mechanism for the excited-state bond-length contraction. In the $4f^7$ ground state, the empty 5d orbitals are antibonding. The bonding counterparts, with main ligand composition and d-type tail, are buried deep inside the stack of doubly occupied orbitals. The $4f \rightarrow 5d$ orbital promotion destabilizes the system in principle, but indirectly favors d-type residual contribution into the bonding orbitals. This is because the lodging of the electron inflates the radial extension across all d-type components. The most favorable situation occurs when the promotion takes place towards the lower d_δ orbitals. Through self-consistency, the slight radial inflation is propagated to the d_π and d_σ orbitals, enhancing their bonding residual contribution, by a better overlap with the ligand orbitals, particularly for the couples made of d_σ and the axial ligand lone pairs. Note that, in the spirit of AOM phenomenology, the d_δ components are expected to be the less bonding and less antibonding contributors in the scheme. When excitation occurs in d_σ , the enhancements in bonding and antibonding effects are mutually canceling, explaining the lesser r_{EuCl} shift in the minima of higher levels energy profiles from Figure 4b.

3.3 The {EuCl₈} unit in idealized cluster systems.

The active center of the SrCl₂:Eu²⁺ materials is an embedded [EuCl₈]⁶⁻ entity. We explored different levels of approximating the environment, excerpting cluster models, the crudest idealization being an isolated [EuCl₈]⁶⁻ unit. This coordination unit may represent semi-quantitatively the main part of ligand field effects, but has the disadvantage of being not stable, because of the large negative charge. However, subtracting from the computed total energies of the coordination unit the value obtained for the enforced ground state of the hypothetical [Cl₈]⁸⁻ cluster, one may obtain minima, at certain sizes of the ligand cube, which can be taken as rough measure of the stabilization due to Eu(II)–Cl interaction. Table 2 shows the results obtained in different technical settings, observing the general retrieval of bond length shrinkage at the 4f → 5d orbital promotion. The Eu–Cl bond lengths are comparable to those obtained for neutral EuCl₂.

Table 2. Computed Eu-Cl bond length fitted for the [EuCl₈]⁶⁻–[Cl₈]⁸⁻ energy difference.

Method	R_{min} (4f ⁷ config), in Å	R_{min} (4f ⁶ 5d ¹ config), in Å
ADF, Restricted, with symmetry and population control	2.695	2.563
ADF, Unrestricted, with symmetry and population control	2.711	2.589
ADF Restricted, without symmetry, with population control	2.694	2.564
ADF Unrestricted, without symmetry, with population control	2.673	2.594
DFT/GTO, Unrestricted, with symmetry, no population control. TD taken as excited f ⁶ d configuration.	2.506	-

CASSCF/GTO/ground state as f^7 case, first excited state as representative for f^6d	2.665	2.621
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Figure 5 shows a graphic representation of the bond length contraction upon excitation as determined by different methods on the $[\text{EuCl}_8]^{6-}$ coordination unit. Note that if the energy of the $\{\text{Cl}_8\}^{8-}$ cluster is not subtracted, the potential energy curves do show minima. Figure 5(a) shows the data from restricted open-shell DFT, performed with the ADF code and employing orbital population averages. In the $4f^7$ ground state, the t_{1u} , t_{2u} , and a_{2u} type ligand field sequence holds unpaired electrons in the restricted treatment, or represents the excess of spin-up functions in unrestricted mode. In the excited configuration, each 4f-type orbital gets the 6/7 fractional occupation, while the components of the 5d-type fivefold are getting, each, the 1/5 occupation. In O_h symmetry, the $4f^7$ and $4f^65d^1$ configurations with smeared orbital occupations give rise to states with different parities in O_h symmetry (odd and even, respectively). As discussed for the EuCl_2 model, the population averaging removes the angular degrees of freedom for degenerate terms. The effective symmetry of the averaged $4f^65d^1$ configuration is ${}^8A_{1g}$, while the ground state transforms as ${}^8A_{1u}$ (which is also the real irreducible representation). Thus, a similarly beneficial situation with different lowest energetic states of varying irreducible representation arises as was already encountered in the linear $[\text{EuCl}_2]$ molecule. Nonetheless, practical problems still arise. For example, an input of 2/5 of the 5d population to enter the e_g -type orbitals in cubic symmetry, while 3/5 are supposed to enter the t_{2g} -type orbitals does not ensure the physically expected energy ordering $E(e_g) < E(t_{2g})$. This is a consequence of the somewhat independent symmetry behavior during the orbital optimization. Then, to obtain the desired energy ordering, we had to introduce an empty e_g set before the fractionally occupied one. One may understand from such notes on particular rectifications that the DFT account of ligand field regime is not systematic and

straightforward, even when additional leverages, like the population control in ADF, are fortunately available.

Figure 5. The potential energy curves, taken as $[\text{EuCl}_8]^{6-} - [\text{Cl}_8]^{8-}$ energy difference, as function of the Eu-Cl bond length: (a) results from restricted DFT/ADF calculations, taken with symmetry and population control; blue line: $4f^7$ ground configuration, red line: $4f^65d^1$ configuration, with one electron averaged over five d-type orbitals; orange dashed lines, the electron promoted in e_g and t_{2g} subsets of 5d orbitals. (b) results from fully-relativistic DFT calculations; the orange dashed lines correspond to controlled promotion into $d_{3/2}$ and $d_{5/2}$ relativistic orbitals. (c) states from CASSCF(7,12) calculations; the f^6d excited levels are grouped in bundles assignable to promotion into e_g and t_{2g} orbitals.

Using frozen orbitals from the fully averaged $4f^65d^1$ calculation, we derived potential energy curves representing the promoted electron in either e_g - or t_{2g} -type orbital species, represented in the lower and upper dashed curves of Figure 5a. The curves labeled as $4f^6e_g$ and $4f^6t_{2g}$ in Figure 5a show minima consistent with that of the $4f^65d^1$ configuration because orbitals from this particular calculation were used. The energy difference between the curves of the $4f^6t_{2g}$ and the $4f^6e_g$ numeric experiments is an estimation of the $10Dq$ gap, placed in the 10000 cm^{-1} range along the represented domain (12550 cm^{-1} at the minimum of the $4f^7$ ground state potential and 10400 cm^{-1} at the respective $4f^65d^1$ minimum). The vertical excitations from $4f^7$ minimum towards the $4f^6e_g$ and $4f^6t_{2g}$ states are about 13900 cm^{-1} and 26450 cm^{-1} , respectively. The estimated de-

excitations, at about 10000 cm⁻¹ and 20400 cm⁻¹. The calculated data underestimate the experimental spectrum, mentioned in the previous section of band structure calculations, suggesting luminescence at much lower energies in the near infrared range. This is, however, not unexpected, given the simplicity of the employed molecular cluster model and neglect of any surrounding host structure. It should be noted, however, that the retrieval of accurate energies was not the purpose of this work but rather the impact on the equilibrium Eu–Cl bond lengths in the ground and excited states, respectively.

Panel (b) of Figure 5 deals with the assessment of DFT fully-relativistic calculations (spin-orbit ZORA formalism). Here, the averaged population is taken over relativistic spin-orbitals. In the free atom, the spin-orbit interaction splits the 5d shell into fourfold degenerate 5d_{3/2} and a sixfold degenerate 5d_{5/2} orbitals, while the 4f shell splits into a sixfold degenerate 4f_{5/2} and an eightfold degenerate 4f_{7/2} orbital, where the subscripts denote the total angular momentum quantum number *j*. The subduction in the representations of the relativistic octahedral double group in Mulliken notation is: d_{3/2} = Γ₈⁺, d_{5/2} = Γ₇⁺ + Γ₈⁺, f_{7/2} = Γ₇⁻ + Γ₈⁻, f_{5/2} = Γ₆⁻ + Γ₇⁻ + Γ₈⁻, the superscripts denoting the behavior at inversion (‘+’ and ‘-’ similar to *g* and *u*, respectively) [78]⁷⁸. Figure 5b shows faulted results, with the 4f⁶5d¹ configuration becoming the ground state at a shorter bond length. We are not aiming here to discover the causes of this failure, confining ourselves to suggest that it may be the case of a wrong account of the Eu atom itself. We noticed that the uncoordinated Eu²⁺ ion without specific control of population in the relativistic orbitals is obtained in a non-physical configuration. Although the global result should not be interpreted with physical content, we considered it interesting to perform the calculations represented with dashed lines in Figure 5b. Namely, by averaging the promoted electron on corresponding double-group representations of relativistic orbital subsets, we emulated the spin-orbit splitting of the 5d shell for the lanthanide

ion in a molecule, performing calculations corresponding to the $4f^6d_{3/2}$ and $4f^6d_{5/2}$ relativistic configurations.

The WFT calculations on the $[\text{EuCl}_8]^{6-}$ simplest model consisted in CASSCF calculations. The subsequent NEVPT2 approach led to wrong results, probably because of the high negative charge is an intrinsic bad conditioning. In spite of the model limitations, the CASSCF results are illustrating the pursued subject of overall molecular volume contraction at excitation. Figure 5c shows that the spin octet states are split in two bundles, with the lower one originating from transitions to the e_g set of d-type orbitals, while the higher one consists of the t_{2g} set. One observes that the lower $4f^6e_g$ states are shifted to shorter bonds, compared to the $4f^7$ ground state, while the whole set of $4f^6t_{2g}$ type shows minima at slightly longer bonds, manifesting a regular behavior of excitation-driven bond elongation. This can be explained in the continuation of rationales debated on the WFT account of the linear EuCl_2 and has also been already demonstrated by WFT calculations and excited state excitation spectroscopy on Tm^{2+} ($4f^{12}5d^1$) in cubic perovskite-type $\text{CsCaBr}_3:\text{Tm}^{2+}$ with octahedrally coordinated $[\text{TmBr}_6]^{4-}$ entities.

The key stays in the fact that the t_{2g} orbitals in a cube are higher in energy, because they contain stronger antibonding σ contributions (in addition to π contributions), while the e_g orbitals contain only π -type antibonding contributions, lower in the energy scheme. In more detail, the symmetry representation of the σ -type group-orbitals (e.g. eight lone pairs pointing radially, from the cube vertices toward the center) consists in the $a_{1g} + a_{2u} + t_{1u} + t_{2g}$ sum. The related set of π -type group orbitals (behaving as the ensemble of couples of axes perpendicular on the metal-ligand radius) is represented as $e_g + e_u + t_{1g} + t_{1u} + t_{2g} + t_{2u}$. Since the t_{2g} representation appears in both σ and π group-orbitals of the ligand, it means the t_{2g} d-type orbitals will participate to both of these bonding

sorts. In turn, the e_g component is contained only in the π ligand group-orbitals, meaning that the d-type set with this symmetry will undergo smaller antibonding perturbation.

The hosting of the promoted electron in the $e_g(d)$ orbitals leads to a slight inflation of their radial extension, and indirectly in the t_{2g} orbitals as well, favoring the bonding contribution of the ligand lone pair having a trace of t_{2g} metal functions, because of an enhanced σ metal-ligand overlap. Obviously, σ -type overlap mostly benefits from an overall orbital inflation, having the most mutually intruding lobes. The incremental radial enhancement of d atomic orbitals, due to the promotion into the π -only antibonding orbitals slightly strengthens the σ -bonding and subtly influences the stack of occupied ligand-predominant orbitals. However, when the promotion occurs into the t_{2g} orbitals, the population of σ -antibonding orbitals diminishes or even reverses this effect, explaining the slight bond elongation in the upper set of potential energy curves (see Figure 5c).

Figure 6. Upper half: different orientations of the coordination unit embedded in a set of pseudopotential atoms and point charges having the size and content of the cubic cell described in Section 3.1. Bottom half: the neutral molecular cluster [EuSr₁₈Cl₃₈] adapted from the computed

$\text{SrCl}_2:\text{Eu}^{2+}$ compound. The selected ensembles obey the octahedral (cubic) symmetry, with O_h point group.

The upgraded level of approximation consisted in a multiconfiguration WFT account of the $[\text{EuCl}_8]^{6-}$ unit, with the next shells of crystal environment introduced in the embedded cluster manner, through capped effective core potentials (cECPs) and point charges (see Figure 6). The cECP boundary consisted in a $\{\text{Sr}_{12}\text{Cl}_{24}\}$ neutral set with atomic charges taken from population analysis of band-structure calculations, +1.834 for Sr and -0.917 for Cl sites. As explained in the caption of Figure 1, drawing a full cubic block implies borrowing atoms from next cells, achieving an excess of strontium sites. For instance, only one corner of the cube pertains to the nominal unit cell, while the other seven ones are repeated by cell-length translations. Since there is an excess of positive centers in the adopted construction, the Sr sites occupying the corners, edges and faces of the cubic cluster were enforced to the +0.707-point charge values, obtaining a neutral ensemble treated fully quantum mechanically, $[\text{EuCl}_8]^{6-}$, embedding layer of cECPs, and point charges. The atomic positions were considered by averaging the resulting geometries of ground and excited configurations from the band structure calculations. In the upper half of Figure 6, the simple point charges were marked with small spheres, the quantum central unit and the ECP layer being represented with larger balls.

The embedded cluster WFT treatments was performed with a CASSCF(7,12) setting (seven electrons in the active space merging the seven f-type orbitals and the five d-type ones), followed by the NEVPT2 second-order perturbational increments. In comparison to the model outlined in Figure 5c, the data presented in Figure 7a show minima at longer bond lengths for all the states. The range of optimized bond lengths is now similar to the full solid-state treatment (see section 3.1) and the embedding is therefore somewhat more realistic. Note that the computed potential energy curves depicted in Figure 7 are direct results of the calculation, without subtraction of the

$\{\text{Cl}_8\}^{8-}$ cluster energy, imposed in the previous instance of the non-embedded $[\text{EuCl}_8]^{6-}$ unit. The minima of the potential energy curves are now consequences of interactions undergone at the expansion of the $[\text{EuCl}_8]^{6-}$ volume against the embedding.

Figure 7. The results from CASSCF/NEVPT2 calculations in embedded cluster technique. (a) $4f^7$ ground state (blue curve) and spin octet excited $4f^65d^1$ states (red lines); (b) spin sextet states, from $4f^7$ configuration (green lines) and with $4f^65d^1$ parentage (magenta lines); (c) spin-orbit (SO) states, computed at equilibrium geometry of the f^7 configuration: the right-side lines are the CAS/PT2/SO levels, the left side showing excited CAS/PT2 sources (with colors convened in previous panels).

Qualitatively, the situation is similar to the calculations presented in reference [79]⁷⁹ for Eu^{2+} -activated fluorite, $\text{CaF}_2:\text{Eu}^{2+}$. Statically-correlated wavefunctions were generated in state-averaged multiconfigurational self-consistent calculations, the dynamic correlation being introduced in perturbational manner, afterwards. The accounted states were described in the technical part, enumerating their parental atomic terms. In ORCA, the highest available symmetry is the abelian D_{2h} group. In this frame, the $4f^7$ configuration spans the A_u symmetry, while the 35 $4f^65d^1$ microstates (either spin octets or sextets) are projected into the $8A_g + 9B_{1g} + 9B_{2g} + 9B_{3g}$ representation. The $4f^7$ sextets are cumulated in the $12A_u + 12B_{1u} + 12B_{2u} + 12B_{3u}$ representation. We also note that one may form $B_1 + B_2 + B_3$ triplets (with u or g subscripts, having equal values of B_1 , B_2 and B_3 energies) arising as formal subduction from T_1 or T_2 octahedral terms, while the A labels, in D_{2h} , may descend from A or E octahedral origin.

Also, in this example, a shorter equilibrium Eu–Cl bond length in the first $4f^6 5d^1$ excited states does appear (see Figure 7a). The optimized ground state bond length is $R_{\text{Eu-Cl}} = 3.188 \text{ \AA}$, the value for the first excited spin-octet state being $R_{\text{Eu-Cl}} = 3.136 \text{ \AA}$. The next congeners from the $4f^6 e_g$ series show comparable geometries. Similar to the situation debated for the previous simpler model of an isolated $[\text{EuCl}_8]^{6-}$ entity, the states emerging from the $4f^6 t_{2g}$ subconfiguration show minima at similar equilibrium bond lengths as the ground state. For instance, the lowest level of this sort has its minimum at $R_{\text{Eu-Cl}} = 3.205 \text{ \AA}$, i.e. slightly expanded than the ground state. Figure 7b depicts spin sextet states. Visual comparison with Figure 7a shows that the spin sextet congeners of the $4f^6 5d^1$ configuration are placed at higher energy and experience a larger ligand field splitting, but with respect of bond length shifts, they follow the same trends described above. Thus, the lowest spin sextet of the $4f^6 e_g$ configuration shows a minimum at a bond length of 3.136 \AA , while the first $4f^6 t_{2g}$ state shows a minimum for a bond length of 3.199 \AA . The spin sextets from excited $4f^7$ states show equilibrium bonds close to that of ground state (between 3.180 \AA and 3.185 \AA) in agreement with expectation.

Figure 7c illustrates the action of spin-orbit on the top of CASSCF and NEVPT2 states, leading to further splitting of octahedral degenerate terms, which can be described by irreducible representations of the octahedral double group. As a normal consequence of this sort of configuration interaction, the spectrum of states spreads, leading to lower energies in the margin of $4f^6 e_g$ set and to higher top states, springing from $4f^6 t_{2g}$. With certain under- or over-estimation of the margins, the center of computed states stays in the experimental range [77]. In order to fix the match with experiment, reference [88] scaled all the calculated energies with 90%, while here, not focusing on the full mimicking of experimental data, we find a semiquantitative retrieval of the physical realism. The dense series of spin-orbit states (in principle mixing together octets and

singlets of both $4f^7$ and $4f^65d^1$ origin) qualitatively explains the experimentally recorded broad bands.

Another modeling, discussed in the following, consists in treating a sufficiently large cluster on a quantum mechanical level, comprising the second and third layers of environment of the Eu(II) ion in the unit cell (aside the first vicinity formed by the eight Cl^- ligands), as shown in the bottom half of the Figure 6. It should be noted that the set of six most outward Cl^- ions (sketching an octahedron in the snippets from bottom row of Figure 6) are artificially imposed (at Sr–Cl distances taken as average over lattice contacts), in order to accomplish a global neutrality of the resulting cluster with simultaneous conservation of the O_h symmetry. These calculations were performed with GAMESS [58⁵⁸] restricted to CASSCF(7,12) as the ensemble is quite demanding for further second-order amendments in this frame. An overview of the modelled system and the resulting electronic states are outlined in Figure 8.

The WFT results on the $[\text{EuSr}_{18}\text{Cl}_{38}]$ cluster seem to reach a level of reasonable comparability with experimental data from luminescence [7⁷Error! Bookmark not defined.] and with the outcome from band structure calculations outlined in the 3.1 section. Thus, the lowest computed excited states, after including spin-orbit interaction are close to the 25000 cm^{-1} margin, retrieving the range found in experiment and solid-state modeling. As discussed in previous cases, the excited states are dichotomized in two sets assignable to the distinct branches of the $4f^7 \rightarrow 4f^65d^1$ transitions, namely into $\{t_{1u}+t_{2u}+a_{2u}\} \rightarrow e_g$ and $\{t_{1u}+t_{2u}+a_{2u}\} \rightarrow t_{2g}$ subsets on a one-electron level (see the right side of Figure 8). The splitting inside each group is modulated by the relatively small gaps due to ligand field within f shell, while the spacing between the barycenters of the two sequences, at about 27500 cm^{-1} and 37000 cm^{-1} , respectively, can be taken simply as a direct measure of the $10Dq$ octahedral gap in the cube, around 9500 cm^{-1} .

To estimate the ligand field schemes of the 4f and 5d shells, we performed the following numeric experiments. The f-type ligand field can be estimated in two ways, by tailored configuration interaction calculations (CI) done with the converged CASSCF orbital sets. The first option is to consider Eu(III) instead of Eu(II), the orbitals remaining frozen, taken from the divalent case, performing then the CI(6,7) calculation that would yield the levels springing from the 7F term of the Eu(III). One may consider such CI as a non-iterative CAS, without SCF. Because the physical problem looks like a hole in a half-filled f-shell, the spectral terms are yielding, actually, the reverse f-type ligand field splitting. Thus, the calculation produces an orbital singlet as ground state, ${}^7A_{2u}$, spaced at 150.4 cm^{-1} and 287.2 cm^{-1} from the orbital triplets ${}^7T_{2u}$ and ${}^7T_{1u}$, respectively. This means that the ligand field splitting of the f orbitals is parametrized by the one-electron state energies $\varepsilon(t_{2u})=0$, $\varepsilon(t_{1u})=136.8\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\varepsilon(a_{2u})=287.2\text{ cm}^{-1}$.

Exactly the same result is obtained by an alternative route. Namely, immediately after the active orbitals list, above the d-type sequence from converged Eu(II) system, one may find a single degenerate orbital with a_{1g} label, mostly deriving from 6s virtual of the metal ion. Then, we generated an active orbital set merging the seven f-type orbitals and this sixth s-type function, performing a calculation with the Eu(II) electron count and its frozen molecular orbitals. The CI(7,8) calculation (seven electrons in the eight orbitals of f+s set) in this artificial model yields 8 states, the first one being the legitimate $4f^7$ ground state of the system, the spacing between the seven excited states repeating a sequence which also can be considered the reverse of ligand field split.

Figure 8. Synopsis of the CASSCF(7,12) calculations accounting for $4f^7$ and $4f^65d^1$ spin-octet spectral states in the $[\text{EuSr}_{18}\text{Cl}_{38}]$ model cluster. Right-side margin: the stack of $4f^65d^1$ excited states. Within the same panel, we represented the barycenters of two energy sequences (lower vs. upper), suggesting their parentage from $4f^6e_g$ and $4f^6t_{2g}$ orbital promotions. Left side: canonical orbitals: f-type in the bottom part and d-type in the upper one. The orbital snippets are zoomed inside the cluster depicted in the lower part of Figure 6.

A trick to obtain the d-type ligand field splitting is suggested in Figure 8, from energy barycenters of the sequenced set of spectral terms. Another computer experiment we performed consisted in constraining the population of the f-type orbitals, occupying with six electrons only the orbital triplet representations, i.e., $(t_{2u})^3(t_{1u})^3(a_{2u})^0$ and thus, enforce an empty a_{2u} -type orbital. This is still kept in the active space. The seventh electron is explicitly forced to occupy the d-type orbitals. The leverages of the used GAMESS code enable such a versatile handling. Then, with the artificially constrained active space, we demanded a single-excitation configuration interaction. The result consists in six states, one restoring the $4f^7$ ground state, the relative energies of the other ones yielding directly the gap between e_g and t_{2g} orbitals. This leads to an estimate of $10Dq = 9060$

cm^{-1} , which is only slightly different from the previous attempt. The obtained orders of magnitude are compatible with the accepted ligand field strengths of 5d and 4f shells [25, 26^{25,26}].

Figure 8 also shows the canonical orbitals of the described CASSCF(7,12) calculation inside the $[\text{EuSr}_{18}\text{Cl}_{38}]$ cluster. One may note the almost pure atomic character of the molecular orbitals with 4f parentage, while the d-type ones are significantly mixed with the ligand environment. This certifies the above suggested feature, that the 4f shell is practically inert from chemical point of view (although crucial in optical and magnetic properties), while the d-type ones are involved in the chemical bonding of the lanthanoid ions in molecules.

4. Conclusions

We presented here a series of computational experiments challenging the academic insight and the computational predicting of complex optical properties related with the lanthanoid luminescence, in the regard of potential use in phosphor materials.

Using a feature newly implemented in the *Quantum Espresso* plane-wave-based DFT code, called “two chemical potentials” (TCP), we emulated the excited state configuration of an Eu(II) ion incorporated into the fluorite-type SrCl_2 host. The TCP is a relatively new technique, yet unexplored in problems similar to the actual one, attracting attention here on this practical aspect. We have consistently found shortened Eu–Cl equilibrium bond length during the $4f^7 \rightarrow 4f^65d^1$ orbital promotion, in contrast to the bond elongation typically encountered in photophysical processes. The explanation consists in the effective involvement of the d-type virtuals in the stabilization of lanthanoid compounds, while the 4f-shell itself is not much involved in the chemical bonding.

We also found that a conventional DFT analysis of the lowest excited state of Eu^{2+} is formally feasible if non-routine strategies of orbital population control specific to the used ADF code are exploited. Post computational tools implemented in ADF (fragment virtual orbitals deletion) illuminated the mechanisms of the observed phenomena. We stress that classic DFT cannot tackle the lanthanoid systems very well, as many 4f configurations result quasi-degenerate ground states, which poses fundamental challenges to DFT based on the Hohenberg-Kohn theorem. The selected case of Eu^{2+} is somewhat special in that regard having an orbitally non-degenerate ground configuration, $4f^7$, but the description of the $4f^65d^1$ excited states is problematic. We showed that the TD-DFT cannot reasonably reach the relevant $4f^7 \rightarrow 4f^65d^1$ -based excitation. Control of the orbital schemes, emulating non-*aufbau* occupations and imposing fractional orbital populations is essential for attaining the desired modeling.

WFT is a most legitimate way to account the multireference electronic structure and properties of lanthanoid-based compounds, accounting for the multi-configurational nature of the electronic states from the onset. This way is available for molecular compounds (coordination complexes), but it can be applied to solid-state problems if an appropriate idealization, i.e. excerpting clusters and designing specific embedding procedure can be applied to activated materials, as we illustrated here on the example of the toy model $\text{SrCl}_2:\text{Eu}^{2+}$. The WFT retrieved the shift to shorter equilibrium bond lengths of potential energy surfaces of the lowest excited $4f^65d^1$ states. Interpreting the data, we found the same mechanism as evidenced by the DFT calculations. The CASSCF treatment is, in general, sufficient to account for lanthanide-based compounds, particularly in problems only related to the 4f shell. However, when the spatially more extended 5d shell is involved, the second-order perturbation (PT2) post-CASSCF corrections enhance the

accuracy. In a reasonably large cluster model, we outlined computational tricks for obtaining the splitting between the 4f and 5d orbitals in the given cubic ligand field.

The presented methodological excursion confronted practical DFT with generally more accurate WFT exposing their intrinsic limits vs. capabilities and contouring a certain complementarity in the face of complex issues, such as lanthanoid-based luminescence in solid, inorganic phosphors.

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